

GAS SELECTION AND FLOW OPTIMIZATION FOR A 1 KHZ TRIGATRON SPARK GAP

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Abstract

This paper discusses the design of a gas flow system for a 1 kHz repetition rate trigatron based spark gap. The system requires a flow rate high enough to clear the gas from the gap in under 1 ms while also maintaining the required operating pressure. The gap is a trigatron based design with an alumina insulated tungsten trigger pin. A 20 kV positive polarity pulse, with a 20 ns risetime, is applied to trigger the main gap which is charged to -40 kV. A brass guard ring is employed to shield the walls of the containment structure from contaminants in order to achieve a longer operational lifetime. Dry air and Nitrogen gasses are tested at various pressures and flow rates. Design considerations, such as inlet and outlet sizing and gap geometry, are taken into account to ensure a high air flow is achieved between the electrodes.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper will look at the design and results of a high flow trigatron spark gap. A center pin trigatron was tested up to 1 kHz. Design issues for higher rep rate were taken into account. This paper presents a design with better flow characteristics. Results are shown for 500 Hz operation. Higher rep rate requires modification to the inlet and outlet of the air flowing through the gap. Results are shown for the same gap using pure nitrogen in addition to dry air.

II. PREVIOUS GAP DESIGN

The gap that is currently used is a center pin trigatron. This design achieves consistent triggering and is able to operate up to 1 kHz. The design employs a center pin surrounded by alumina insulation. The opposite electrode opposes the adjacent and is charged to -40 kV. This geometry can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1: Center Pin Trigatron

The gap is cleared by flowing air normal to the gap spacing straight through the chamber. The air flow required is approximately 7 SCFM at 45 psi. Additionally, brass guard rings are used to prevent ablation caused by breakdown and increase longevity of the gap. The two electrodes are approximately 7 mm apart. This design while able to achieve 1 kHz is unable to sustain higher rep rates. The electrodes being close together create a high velocity area which reduces pressure. As pressure and flow are increased further for high rep rate the pressure drops between the electrodes due to the Bernoulli principle.

III. SECOND GAP DESIGN

The second gap addressed the design faults in the first gap, namely the airflow. The second gap is a cylindrical gap design with a ring used as the opposite electrode. The cylindrical design allows for the air to flow relatively unimpeded between the adjacent and opposite electrode. The trigger pin was removed from the adjacent electrode and placed approximately 30 mils away normal to the adjacent electrode face. This allows for small adjustment in the spacing and greater gap precision. This design was found to be problematic since it was difficult to reliably trigger the gap. Figure 2 shows the circuit. The 110 k Ω resistor is used to reference the output to the trigger so that the adjacent electrode does not float up when the high voltage is charged.

Figure 2: Opposite Trigger Design

The spacing of the electrode from the trigger was determined based on simulations done in COMSOL. The previous design gap was modeled and the static electric field intensity was measured. The opposite facing trigger was also modeled. The spacing was determined based on similar electric field potentials. The design of the first gap allowed for surface flashover between the trigger alumina and the electrode. With no surface flashover, the trigger pin was unable to consistently spark which was crucial in this design. This gap was able to achieve higher air flow and clear the gap better. However, due to the gap not breaking from the trigger, it was unable to operate above 100 Hz.

IV. FINAL DESIGN

The final design incorporated the cylindrical design of the second gap while also achieving surface flashover similar to the first gap. A cross-section can be seen in figure 3.

Figure 3: Current Trigger Design

The trigger is run through the electrode surrounded by a sleeve of Teflon insulation. The sleeve is one solid piece and restricts the trigger from breaking anywhere but the outside of the electrode. This design causes the gap to break more consistently. The flashover has greatly increased the pressure the gap will break at. In addition the electrode is in closer proximity to the charging ring.

This has shown that if the trigger does not arc, the electric field disturbance is enough to break the gap. This gap is able to achieve 500 Hz operation. There are still air flow issues that are restricting the operation up to 1 kHz. The air inlet and outlet are input to the gap from the side of the chamber at a 90 degree angle. This forms a low pressure area between the electrode opposite the outlet. Results of the 500 Hz operation can be seen in figure 4. The gap consistently breaks at the charge voltage of -40 kV.

Figure 4: Air 500 Hz Operation

Figure 4 shows the pressure for 500 Hz was approximately 45 psi. The flow was less than 5 SCFM and was below the bottom limit of the flow meter.

V. GAS TESTING

Along with dry air, Nitrogen was also tested in the gap. The Nitrogen proved more difficult to achieve high rep rate. One possible reason for this is Oxygen helps recombine with the ionized particles and allows the gap to reset quicker [1]. Figure 5 shows the operation of the gap at 500 Hz with nitrogen.

Figure 5: Nitrogen 500 Hz

One can see the Nitrogen performs very poorly compared to the dry air. Double the flow is needed to get any results. This again points to oxygen performing better at scavenging electrons. further into the 100 shots the gap

performance suffered. The final shots of the gap can be seen breaking at only -25 kV. Further testing will be done with different gases, SF₆ for example, while very good at hold off and scavenging electrons would be too costly for flowing in a gap.

VI. SUMMARY

In conclusion the new high flow gap has achieved 500 Hz operation. Further data is needed to achieve greater repetition rates than 1 kHz. COMSOL simulations will be run to determine flow rates and minimize turbulent flow. Alumina or a suitable more rugged insulator is desirable to replace the Teflon in use now. Further gas testing will need to be conducted, including various percentages of Oxygen with Nitrogen.

VII. REFERENCES

[1] C. Yeh, 'Voltage Recovery Studies for a High Energy Spark Gap', Ph.D., Texas Tech University, 1984.